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Urban Women and Entrepreneurial Venture: A Few Cases of Women Entrepreneurs of Kolhapur Maharashtra

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Abstract

Women are the nuclei of a nation. They are the real builders and moulders of a nation's destiny. The position and status of women in any society is an index of its civilization and progress. A women entrepreneur is a person who is an enterprising individual with an eye for opportunities and an uncanny vision, commercial acumen with tremendous perseverance and above all a person who is willing to take risk with the unknown because of the adventurous spirit she possess. Women are competent in running business but due to hurdles in the form of social, cultural and economic reasons, they lack behind. In spite of women empowerment movement in the country, there is the lack of entrepreneurial ecosystem.

In spite of having the potential and talent, women is deprived of opportunities, information and education. Today business is built around human capital and women are one of the valuable factor. Many of the enterprise run by the women are able to create a successful business out of something as mundane as cooking. Despite being untrained, they are able to make their business a success because of their discipline and commitment; but the potentiality and talent among the women is not identified adequately.

At this critical juncture when the job market is down; these aspiring women entrepreneurs can be encouraged to set up enterprises so that, apart from being independent they can also employ people in their workforce. In the long run, these women can be the backbone of the regional as well as national economy.

The cases mentioned below are of women entrepreneurs from Kolhapur, Maharashtra. The researcher aims to identify and highlight the potentialities of women entrepreneurs and make them a source of motivation for other women to take up entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Urban Entrepreneurship, Women Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial Venture, Economic Development, Aatmnirbhar Bharat

1. Cases of Women Entrepreneurs.

- 1) **Mrs. Nima Kamble**, a post graduate by qualification runs a school from play group to standard 4th and has also got permission to teach up to std 7th. She happened to come into the education field accidentally. Nima's husband, an officer in Union Bank of India had got transferred to Ainapur, a village near Miraj. The condition of a primary school close to her house was very bad with just a few teachers running the whole show. She came in touch with a few responsible people there, who were influenced by her good, understanding nature, apart from that she was an officer's wife and educated too. She was requested to help in the development of that school, by taking it under her charge. She accepted it and thus her entry into education field. She proved to be a dedicated teacher and was managing all the things very well.

After a year her husband got transferred to Kolhapur and the whole family had to be shifted to Kolhapur, Nima felt sad to leave that school as things had started to settle well there. She came to Kolhapur fully inspired by her experience at Ainapur and planned to start with a play group in her house here. There was a good response to the play group, with initially 20 children enrolled. She managed it all alone with the help of two maids. The locality where she was staying was of a lower middle class, thus there was a problem of fee recovery. At times she had to forego the fees looking at the economic condition of the parents. She became very well known in the vicinity, now she planned to pool in more teachers and start classes up to 4th standard. She

approached the government authorities for the permission to increase the classes up to 4th standard, she was given the permission on the condition that she will not ask for any help in the form of grants or subsidy from the government as this will come under the non-grantable scheme.

Nima did not deter, she stood strong and without any expectation from the government she tried to raise the resources required and went forward with her ambitions. Her work was appreciated by others and today she has expanded her school in a rented premises up to 4th std and has also got permission for running the school up to 7th std. Today she employs 12 female teachers.

Her advice to the budding women entrepreneurs is 'make a complete study of the field one wants to enter into, study its advantages, disadvantages and also commitments to give justice to your work.

- 2) **Mrs. Nilima Kesarkar**, educated up to 11th standard, her husband had a grain and grocery shop. Due to some fight in the house with his father, he left the house and was not found anywhere, Mrs. Nilima had 3 daughters and a new born son in her responsibility, she had no where to look, her daughters were then school going. With great courage to secure a good future for her children, she asked her father-in-law to allow her to run her husband's shop. Instead of supporting her view and helping her, he was upset with her decision. Nilima knew that the shop was in her husband's name so she gathered courage and decided to run the shop, the father-in-law was very angry with her as she had not respected his decision. He told their grain suppliers not to grant Nilima any credit for the purchases she makes and if they did so, it must be on their own responsibility, as she being a lady and again inexperienced in this trade, he did not have confidence on her ability.

Nilima was denied credit and finally she had to mortgage her jewellery to buy the grains on credit. She found it difficult initially to deal with the truck and tempo drivers for transporting her purchase to the shop from the mills. She put up a very brave front and dealt with all such situations which she had never handled earlier as her husband was looking after everything. Her entry into this entrepreneurial venture was due the push factor, she was pushed to take up entrepreneurship so as to tide up with economic difficulties. After this she did not look behind, she gained confidence of her suppliers; she was supported by her elder twodaughters as they use to assist her after school hours. Now she has got a good credit standing in the market, she can get easily credit up to 25-50 lakhs. She has also added spices, soap, pickles etc. to the grains and pulses stock. All the other products also have a good demand. She has made permanent customers and presently her annual turnover has risen up to 50-60 lakhs. She has got all her daughters married off and now the son has grown big enough to shoulder and head the business.

Her advice to the budding women entrepreneurs is ‘Trust your instincts and act on it’ and be patient as success does not happen overnight.

- 3) **Mrs. Seema Shah**, proprietor of ‘Mohak Lassi Centre’, a graduate of commerce. She started on a place owned by her in-laws, thus investment in land was not required, but working capital was to be raised. She planned to avail the P.M.R.Y (Prime Minister Rozgar Yojana) and get loan on a meagre interest rate. When she approached the officer in charge with her proposal, the officer was suspicious about her ability to repay the loan as she was a woman and he was doubtful about, how far a lassi centre can be successful. She was only sanctioned Rs 90,000 and he kept back the remaining 10,000/- rupees.

Seema accepted the challenge of the situation and with her hard work and entrepreneurial ability repaid the loan in a years time, she proudly says that the same bank has given her a loan of Rs 10,00,000/-today. She has bought diversification by adding 2-3 more eatable items along with lassi, added some flavor in lassi and is now planning for ISO9001:2000:2008. She has ordered special equipment from Germany, an industrial dish washer which washes 3300 plates in an hour and the plates will be bacteria free. Another automated machine to boil, clean and mash potatoes and a vegetable cutting machine.

She is also planning to go for HACCP (Hazard Analysis Critical Control Plant).Today she has roped in her family members too in the business and is providing employment to 25 people. She is the member of Maharashtra Chamber of Commerce and also delivers guest lectures on entrepreneurship in management colleges.

- 4) **Ms. Heena Patel** had just passed her graduation from Sourashtra University when she got married; she was married in Kolhapur, in a middle class Gujarati family having a grain and salt business. It was a joint family where all three brothers along with their family and parents stayed together. She was a committed housewife till she was a mother of two sons.She use to see her illiterate cousins, living in Gujarat making papad and pickles and doing some earnings, she thought they being illiterate can make a living so why can't she. In the meantime Heena's elder brother-in-law was found to be suffering from cancer; this illness of him disturbed the whole family mentally and financially. The treatment being costly,the family faced severe financial problems.

This incidence gave her inner hidden desire a concrete base as she decided that something must be done. Thus she planned to start with preparing Srikhand along with her cousin sister who was in Kolhapur in partnership, they planned to sell it to the small sweet marts but it could not be a success, she did not give up, she planned to

start with making ice-cream, as Heena's cousin in Ahmadabad had a ice-cream parlor which was running very well, she thought she could learn from him and start on similar lines in Kolhapur. She went to learn from him but was surprised at the lukewarm response from her cousin; he said that it was a morning 6 am to 12 pm job and not a women's cup of tea. Heena persisted and stayed there for 8 days, she used to just observe and understand the things, though he used to hide some processes from her, like proportion of some powder that needed to be mixed with milk so that ice crystals are not formed in the ice-cream etc. Finally just to please her, the cousin said that she can buy a churner, a boiler to boil milk, a deep fridge and he will come down to Kolhapur to help her in setting up an ice-cream parlor.

Heena fully charged and high on her expectations decided to purchase these minimum required equipments. But where will the money come from? Was a big question. It required investment of around 4 to 5 lakhs. She talked to her cousin partner, whether they could go together for this venture too. She agreed and then they decided to arrange the funds, Heena remembers that she had asked her parents not to give any gifts to her children at their birth, instead keep an amount in fixed deposit for the child. Today she planned to break that deposit and use it as capital for her business. Finally she started her own ice-cream shop in the basement of her house in Kolhapur. The ice-cream did not turn out well, there was formation of ice crystals in the ice-cream, but she did not lose hope, she joined an ice-cream making classes and overcame her mistake.

Today she is a successful entrepreneur, she had to face problems from food inspectors and police also, They trouble on unnecessary and baseless pretexts, but her entrepreneurial verve could not discourage her passion and now she stands proudly on her shop counter, her husband also later joined her as he incurred a loss in the business

he started after the joint family separated. She is proud enough to be the proprietor of her small business which is fetching a daily average collection of Rs 15000. She has 10 employees working for her ice-cream parlour. She needs around 300-500 litres of milk per day during normal days and about 1000-2000 litres during seasons. She says confidently that dedication and determination can fetch anything in life. Today she makes 25 flavors in ice creams apart from sundaes, cocktails, casatas, milk shakes etc. she also sells curds, shrikhand, khava. She is a proud recipient of ‘Sammaniya Vyapari puraskar’ an award installed by the Rajarampuri Vyapari Association. She proudly says ‘I am happy I have made a community of my own, I know so many people and people know me for my quality ice creams and respect me, my hard work is rewarded’.

2. Some of the tips given by these Women Entrepreneurs are

Table1. 12 Tips for Entrepreneurship – From collective experiences

Put all your E nergy into your idea, love what you do.
D elegate - have a team, don't try to do it all yourself.
L earn as quickly as you can.
Be a creative T hinker.
B elieve in yourself.
Pay attention to details and make all R elationships a win-win arrangement.
Find a great M entor.
Focus on where the M oney will come from and keep it a priority.
Keep going, you need to be P ersistent.
Enjoy the journey of life and be P atient as success does not happen overnight.
Take R esponsibility.
T rust your instincts and act on it.

3. Conclusion

A large number of women around the world have set up and managed their own businesses. It was not easy for these women to succeed in business. They had to face a lot of difficulties and overcome a number of barriers to become successful in their ventures. They had to deal with discrimination and withstand the skepticism of society and also put in more effort than men to prove their credibility to others.

Empowering women entrepreneurs is essential for achieving the goals of sustainable development. The bottlenecks hindering their growth must be eradicated to entitle their full participation in the business. Apart from training programs, newsletters, mentoring, trade fairs and exhibitions also can help as a source for their entrepreneurial development. It is seen that promoting entrepreneurship among women will certainly be a short-cut to rapid economic growth and development.

Women today are radiating that unmistakable glow of leadership. The time has come for the nations to celebrate and salute the success of women. The country should rise to the challenge and create more support systems for encouraging more entrepreneurship amongst women. At the same time, women should break away from stereotyped mindsets.

Let us try to eliminate all forms of gender discrimination and thus allow **‘women’** to be an entrepreneur at par with men

3.1 Questions

Q1) what characteristics of entrepreneurs are seen in each of the case?

Q2) Discuss the problem and prospects of an women entrepreneur

Q3) Justify the importance of women empowerment for Indian entrepreneurship development.

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